

SSHOC-NL T4.2 deliverable 2024-D01: Report on SSH Data Deposit Workflows

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Introduction

In this report, a set of use cases and requirements is described for basic data deposit workflows, which will allow for extensions to be added for use among different communities within the Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH) domain. This is part of task 4.2 of the SSHOC-NL project¹. The task aims to develop mechanisms which connect datasets in the SSH-domain to resources that are instrumental in making datasets FAIR, such as vocabularies. More specifically, the workflow reported on in this document relates to subtask 1 of task 4.2, which has the following aim: *for researchers within the SSH-domain, community specific user interfaces will be developed for depositing, enriching, and publishing their research data. For this, a workflow will be elaborated for archiving and publishing datasets, providing metadata drawing on controlled vocabularies (see task 4.1), invoking web services for processing files and adding annotations (see task 3.1). This will be coordinated with task 1.1 for the computational requirements of invoking web services, for e.g. automated transcription of audio and video files.*

This document is intended for use both internally, within DANS, and externally, by the outside world. Internally, the report should give direction to the planning of the work conducted in DANS around deposit workflows during the years 2025-2028. Externally, it may serve to account for choices DANS subsequently makes in the development of deposit workflows, as well as inspire other service providers of data management infrastructure to collaborate with DANS and/or further develop their own data deposit workflows. The report is the result of the exploratory work done during the first year of the SSHOC-NL project. It consists of two parts: (1) community input from data stewards and other research support staff, and (2) analysis of current data deposit workflows. These activities will be described in more detail in the following sections.

¹ <https://sshoc.nl/>

1. User needs for data deposit workflows

The first community input activity of task 4.2 subtask 1 was a session on SSH data deposit workflows, organised in October 2024. The aim of the session was to translate insights, experiences, and needs with regards to the archiving and publishing of SSH research data (either to DANS Data Stations², DataverseNL³, or other trustworthy digital repositories) into actionable plans for improvement of such data deposit workflows. To achieve this, data stewards and other research support staff who work with Dutch researchers within the SSH-domain were invited to join the session to provide their input.

To prepare for the session, we sent out a questionnaire to the invitees, to be filled out before the session. Out of 15 invitees among data stewards and research support staff, 7 responded to the request. Questions covered topics such as reasons for publishing/archiving data, selection of platforms, licences, technical requirements, and user-friendliness. The full questionnaire can be found in the Appendix. Based on the answers⁴, we identified three main topics for discussion: (1) improving functionalities, (2) working with restricted data, and (3) getting support, which will be discussed in more detail below.

As an introduction to these three main topics, we had a more general discussion on archiving and publishing SSH research data. During this discussion, attendees pointed out that the policy around archiving and publishing research data differs per institute, but in many cases is also quite vague:

- at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU), the policy is to store the data somewhere, but it does not specify any other conditions.
- at the University of Groningen (RUG), the policy stops at local archiving, generally with no way to add metadata or Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and consequently little concern for long term preservation.
- At Maastricht University (UM), the policy encourages researchers to publish at least metadata (whenever possible), but whether they actually do so remains unclear.

Even though our sample was small, these observations suggest that there is a lot of diversity and uncertainty about archiving and publishing policies and practices in the Dutch research landscape.

Furthermore, the concern was raised by attendees that even though the institute – rather than the individual researcher – is the legal rightsholder of the research data, institutes are generally blind to what the researcher is doing in practice. This **lack of control** is considered to be problematic. In practice this is experienced by research support staff. For example, at the Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR), researchers that collect and publish anonymous data – which can be openly shared – hardly ever contact the data stewards. Support staff generally only encounter researchers that work with sensitive data.

² <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-stations/>

³ <https://dataverse.nl/>

⁴ Questionnaire respondents and/or session attendees are listed as contributors to this report

The lack of contact between researchers and data stewards can hinder good archiving practices. One example shared was that researchers can become **unduly anxious** by design choices, such as the *publish* button in Yoda.⁵ This anxiety could easily be alleviated by their data stewards explaining that pressing the *publish* button in Yoda does not necessarily mean that the research data becomes openly available. If researchers learn that they have the option to publish their data with restricted access, or to publish only the metadata and supporting materials, they generally become less hesitant in sharing (parts of) their data.

One way to ensure that research data is properly stored at the end of the research phase is by enforcing the submission of so-called **Data Availability Statements (DASs)**. At the RUG, drafting a DAS⁶ was added as one of the steps to be completed within Hora Finita⁷, the PhD tracking system. Adding this step resulted in an increase in data archiving, at least at the local level. The VU also indicated that they have a DAS template that they can share.

Finally, a point about the **retention period** of research data was brought up. Specifically, there is some uncertainty about the lifespan of reusability of data: when it is time to pull the plug or put data in hibernation mode.

1a. Improving functionalities

One of the main topics discussed during the session was which functionalities in data management systems and repositories need improvement, and in which sense. We discussed the possibility of **connecting platforms**, so that researchers can automatically move their data from the platform that they use during the research phase to another platform for archiving and/or publication. The question was raised whether the benefits of linking platforms outweigh the investment required, which will be the responsibility of DANS to investigate further. Whether or not such improvements will also result in an increase in data deposits remains unclear at this stage.

Currently, the VU stays within the Yoda environment, which the VU support staff considers to be a success among researchers. Yoda includes a data curation step. Currently it is not possible to deposit data from within Yoda directly to a repository (even though there are plans for creating a solution for this, for which funding is currently being sought). As a temporary solution, for institutes that use Yoda for data storage during the research phase, but that use DANS services such as the DANS Data Stations or DataverseNL to publish their data, it would be useful to have the possibility to download the metadata from Yoda and upload it directly to DANS. Currently, this is possible through an API, but DANS might assess the feasibility of allowing users to also do this through the web interface.

Conversely, the RUG has developed its own Research Data Management System (RDMS)⁸ and is currently running tests on the possibility of connecting the RDMS to DataverseNL through an Application Programming Interface (API). The downside of this is that the

⁵ <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/yoda-hosting>

⁶ <https://www.rug.nl/digital-competence-centre/research-data/archive-and-publish/>

⁷ <https://www.rug.nl/education/phd-programmes/during/hora-finita>

⁸ <https://wiki.hpc.rug.nl/rdms/start>

content cannot be checked by the RUG DataverseNL support team, as they can only check on metadata level. This limits the possibilities of data curation – even for curation on a metadata level only, it would be convenient to at least have access to the content of the dataset.

In addition to the general discussion on the topic of improving functionalities, we also formulated a number of user stories on this topic. These user stories provide additional guidance in the further development of our services.

Rather than reporting them integrally here, the user stories have been taken into account in the 'Recommendations'-section below (1e.), and added integrally at the end of this report, in Appendix B.

1b. Working with restricted access data

Another topic that sparked a lot of debate was working with restricted access data, especially regarding licences for re-use of such data. Ideally, such a license will specify conditions for re-use in a more fine-grained manner than currently possible. For instance, the license might allow for the re-use of the data for research or educational purposes, limited to the European Economic Area (EEA), stipulating that the data cannot be shared further. Currently, there is no model licence for such conditions. Institutes tend to write their own custom licences, which is a time-consuming process.

Relatedly, at the RUG, there currently is an elaborate access procedure⁹ in place for restricted access data with custom terms. This procedure involves many parties (i.e., researcher, data steward, privacy officer, legal advisor, managing director of the faculty) and a lot of steps, including the signing of a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA), which, again, is a time-consuming process. However, even with a DTA in place, trust is needed. When access is given to a restricted access dataset, it cannot be guaranteed that the person receiving the data will act according to the enforced conditions.

It should become clear what the risks are of sharing restricted data. In order to achieve this, a risk classification system could be used. However, current classification systems are for operational systems and are not necessarily geared towards data.

For this topic yet another set of user stories were generated, included in the 'Recommendations'-section below (1e.), and can be found integrally in Appendix B.

1c. Getting support

Lastly, we discussed the topic of getting support, mainly with regards to DataverseNL. The experience of attendees currently is that DANS is supportive and quick to pick up issues. However, the DataverseNL network could be improved and expanded. That way, members

⁹ <https://www.rug.nl/digital-competence-centre/research-data/archive-and-publish/make-your-data-available-under-restricted-access>

of the network can also use each other as a knowledge base, in addition to rather than having to rely solely on support they receive from DANS.

Two user stories concerning getting support have been added in Appendix B.

1d. Follow-up session

After the session described above, there was another occasion to get input on deposit needs, organised during the DANS Open Day on 14 November 2024¹⁰. At the Open Day a mix of data stewards, infrastructure service providers and some policy makers and researchers were present. At a workshop during the Open Day, some 30 people were introduced to the concept of deposit pipelines¹¹: connections between components of the digital research infrastructure, which allow users to perform research data management tasks and deposit their data for archiving and publication in one go. In the second half of the workshop, participants were invited to create user stories outlining functionalities they would like to integrate into deposit pipelines.

It should be realised that the user stories (see appendix B) collected during the DANS Open Day workshop were articulated within a more restricted conceptual framework. The workshop revolved around the concept of ‘deposit pipelines’.¹² It presupposed a particular approach towards integration of data repositories with other components of a research infrastructure. This approach entails the creation of parallel user interfaces, to perform data operations that fall outside the functionality of the data archive software, Dataverse. The participants giving their input on needs and requirements were therefore already conditioned to do so within this framework of deposit pipelines.

The user stories have been summarised below and can be read in their entirety in Appendix B.

1e. Recommendations

The findings emerging from the discussions (at the session and open day workshop) and from the user stories are summarised in this section, as recommendations.

The actual practice of data deposit for archiving and publishing research data, making them available for reproduction and reuse, is still not a generalized practice in the Social Sciences and Humanities, notwithstanding requirements for depositing being in place in the policies of funding agencies and research organisations. This is due, for a large part, to a lack of awareness about available facilities, unwarranted concerns about privacy, but also to shortcomings in the existing infrastructure.

¹⁰ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/dans-open-day-2024/>

¹¹ Touber, J. (2024, November 14). Deposit Pipelines (DANS Open Day, November 14th, 2024). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14143028>.

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/14143028>

Improvements to work on within SSHOC-NL

Improvements which would promote data archiving and publication for reuse within the Social Sciences and Humanities are, in part, about introducing or streamlining procedures and making documentation easier to find. They also include some technical developments. Finally a few topics have emerged which require further exploration, before deciding to turn them into actual requirements. To improve the situation the following recommendations are formulated (unless stated otherwise, the recommendations are addressed to DANS as the provider of repository services):

Procedures and documentation

- Offer a more refined set of licences for reuse in data repositories. Currently, repositories have a rather limited offering of data access licences which depositors can choose from. Depositors require a more fine-grained range of options to choose from, preferably in a modular way which allows depositors to assemble a custom licence which is suitable for their type of research data.
- Better guidance for depositors in selecting a repository when archiving data and code, including a coherent set of succinct and clear descriptions of available repository services. This would lower the burden to researchers and data stewards of finding the right places to go to.
- Better guidance for depositors in getting their data and code into the proper formats before depositing them. This information is already available, but it might be provided to the depositors in a more proactive manner.
- The procedure for access to research data subject to restricted access conditions should be made crystal clear, both to end users and to the data stewards who support the depositors. The practice of completing Data Access Protocols (DAPs) should go some way to satisfying this requirement, since a DAP specifies in detail how an end user can gain access to a dataset with restricted access.¹³
- Elaborate a risk classification system for research data, analogous to the risk classification system currently in place for operational systems. This would give researchers hesitant to publish their data some firm footing with regard to the threat of their data inadvertently falling into the wrong hands. It would also allow for more informed decisions about whether or not to publish data in the first place.
- Promote the practice of submitting Data Availability Statements (DASs), for instance as an annexe to be added to a Data Management Plan after the end of a research project. The policy to require submission of a DAS before being allowed to defend a PhD-thesis, as currently adopted by the University of Groningen, would be a good starting point.

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14516380>

Technical development

- Direct connections between project research environments and project data storage, on the one hand, and archival platforms, on the other, allowing researchers to deposit their data directly into a repository from the environment where the data live during a research project, would benefit increased deposit and availability of data.
- When depositing a dataset into a repository, some of the metadata which are already available in source systems such as Preregistrations, Data Management Plans, Software Management Plans, Research Information Systems, lab journals, scripts, privacy assessments and publications, might be provided with the data deposit, together with all Persistent Identifiers, to standardise metadata descriptions and prevent loss of time due to double work.
- Introduce a feature to repositories for ingesting metadata from somewhere else (e.g. research environment, CRIS, DMP). It would improve FAIRness of data and other research objects.
- Allow depositors to link research software to their dataset via Persistent Identifiers. In ways that those relations are visible in data aggregators such as DataCite PIDGraph or OpenAIRE Research Graph.
- A feature in Dataverse to change the folder structure of data files in a dataset which has already been deposited. This would increase the flexibility of the depositor, allowing them to optimise the structure of their deposit directly within Dataverse.

Issues which require further exploration

- What is a sensible lifespan for research data? Do research data have an expiry date? Is there a difference in longevity between different kinds of research data? Can criteria for selection and retention be defined? How does this translate into retention periods for different classes of research data?
- To what extent is it possible to extract variable information and value ranges from a dataset? Is this confined to tabular data? What is the most convenient way to make this information available? Could an explicit, language agnostic description of the data (schema), such as the approach proposed by LinkML, be a route to increase the findability and interoperability of the data?"
- Is it possible to automate the detection of personal or otherwise sensitive data within a dataset, for researchers or data stewards to be alerted before submitting the dataset to a repository? This would allow them more easily to choose the proper repository, access conditions and licence for reuse.

2. Existing concepts of data deposit workflows

The previous section discussed existing needs and wishes with regard to data deposit within the SSH-domain. In parallel, data deposit workflows currently deployed, or being experimented with, have been explored, to judge which are the most promising scenarios for realising some of the needs which emerged from the community input. It is worthwhile to investigate which workflow pipelines already exist and to dive into the current developments that are already underway. This to avoid double work, to learn from the experiences of others, and to see where DANS can add value.

Our investigation has focused on connections with the Dataverse software, because this is where DANS's expertise lies, but also because the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities – based on Dataverse software – is a key repository in The Netherlands for the SSH domain. Although the tools and connections will not always be fully compatible with other software and services, most of the principles will remain the same for other integrations.

2a. Overview of known deposit connections with Dataverse software

When thinking about existing deposit workflows, of course the most obvious method is uploading from the local storage of a researcher's computer, via the User Interface of the repository. But after some brainstorming, it became clear there are many other ways for a depositor to upload data to a repository, as well. These are listed below.

While compiling the list below, it became clear that we could distinguish between two different types of tools. Some workflows are based on a **push mechanism** (data is sent from the tool/platform where the data was stored during the research phase to the designated repository), while others use a **pull mechanism**. With a pull mechanism, the main focus is on the designated repository and the tool/platform lets the user collect the files that are needed for the dataset in order to complete the deposit. With a push mechanism, your workflow starts where the depositor has his data stored.

#	Start of Deposit Workflow	pull / push	Description	Remarks
1	DANS Data Station deposit form	pull	With the 'add files' button in the User Interface the files can be added to a dataset from local storage, Dropbox, Research Drive or any other source that is reachable from someone's personal computer.	
2	OH-SMArt ¹⁴	pull	A deposit form with added metadata fields for the Oral History domain.	Although files are pushed into the Data Station, the customer's experience is similar to a pull action. Files have to be selected by the depositor with drag and drop, or by selecting files.
3	DANS Repository Selector ¹⁵	pull	The depositor first goes down a decision tree to select a relevant repository, and then is confronted with a form to fill in metadata and select files.	Although files are pushed into the Data Station, the customer's experience is similar to a pull action. (Files have to be selected from another source.)
4	SRDC: SURF Research Data Connector ¹⁶	push	A depositor can connect SURF Research Drive with Dataverse, Figshare, Zenodo or OSF to upload a folder to a new dataset.	The tool also supports download of datasets from the Data Station to Research Drive.
5	iRods/ Yoda	push	Repositories based on iRODS can be connected with the Dataverse API to send data from iRODS to Dataverse. Depending on the code that is used, this can be a fully automatic process, or a manual process (by clicking a button to start the process.)	Existing known connections are Maastricht MUMC iRods to DataverseNL, Amsterdam UMC Yoda to DataverseNL.
6	Github ¹⁷	push	This action automatically uploads GitHub repository content to a Dataverse dataset. It can upload the entire repository or its subdirectories to dataverse.	GitHub users will need to configure their GitHub repo themselves to be able to make a connection.

#	Start of Deposit Workflow	pull / push	Description	Remarks
7	Dropbox	pull	Within the dataverse software, it is possible to let users click a 'upload from Dropbox' button to select files directly from dropbox.	
8	Dataverse Integration Dashboard ¹⁸	pull	The integration dashboard is set up as a tool to pull data from existing active data management tools. Currently supported are iRODS, Gitlab, GitHub, OSF, Sharepoint, SFTP.	Software developed by KU Leuven, for their own Dataverse. The code is Open Source, so reusable for other Dataverse instances.
9	SWORD ¹⁹	push	Users can use the SWORD protocol to send and publish data in Dataverse.	There is no User Interface, but this protocol can be used within other applications.
10	Open Science Framework (OSF) ²⁰	push	OSF offers a plug-in to connect to Dataverse so that files uploaded or updated in OSF are also updated in the corresponding dataset in Dataverse.	
11	DVUploader ²¹	push	A command line tool to upload files to Dataverse, as an alternative to the web interface if there are lots of files to upload, large files, or if a complicated directory structure is needed.	No user interface available, but there is work in progress to create a plug-in with an interface. See demo .

Beside the integration mentioned in the table above, the Dataverse community also worked on other integrations. To get data from other platforms into Dataverse, there are tools for

¹⁴ <https://ohsmart.datastations.nl/> (accessed 28-10-2024)

¹⁵ <https://4tu.dansdemo.nl/> (accessed 28-10-2024)

¹⁶ <https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=102828271> (accessed 31/10/2024)

¹⁷ <https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse-uploader> (accessed 31/10/2024)

¹⁸ <https://www.kuleuven.be/rdm/en/rdr/integration-dashboard> (accessed 31/10/2024)

¹⁹ <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/api/sword.html#sword-api> (accessed 31/10/2024)

²⁰ <https://help.osf.io/article/208-connect-dataverse-to-a-project> (accessed 31/10/2024)

²¹ <https://github.com/GlobalDataverseCommunityConsortium/dataverse-uploader/wiki/DVUploader,-a-Command-line-Bulk-Uploader-for-Dataverse> (accessed 31/10/2024)

RSpace, Open Journal Systems (OJS), Renku, Amnesia, SampleDB, RedCap, GitLab, Globus and DataLad. Furthermore there are integrations in the context of Research Data Preservation like Archivematica and 'RDA BagIt (BagPack) Archiving'. Since this report focuses on depositing data, other integration categories (like 'Analysis and Computation' and Discoverability) are not in scope.

Of the connections listed in the table above, we have taken a more profound look at the SURF Research Data Connector and the Dataverse Integration Dashboard. Both platforms have a dedicated user interface, and can be clearly defined as push (SRDC) or pull (Integration Dashboard).

SURF Research Data Connector (SRDC)

The SRDC is still in its pilot phase, but is already available for testing. In short, the fundamental functionality works as follows:

The user with access to SURF Research Drive can find the 'SRDC' icon within the Research Drive navigation menu. First, you will need to connect with the repository of your choice. For a Dataverse-based repository, this means that the user will have to copy their personal API-Token from the Dataverse repository's web interface into the SRDC page (this needs to be done only the first time that the SRDC is being used). Once connected, the user can select a folder that contains the files that need to be uploaded. The user must choose the destination collection (sub-dataverse) and fill in the required metadata fields. As a result, a new dataset will be created with the selected files in it.

To publish the dataset and to add more metadata, the user will have to browse to the dataset in the Dataverse repository and perform the actions there.

Dataverse Integration Dashboard (KU Leuven)

The Dataverse Integration Dashboard was developed by the KU Leuven. The Dashboard connects several data sources to the RDR (Research Data Repository of the KU Leuven, based on Dataverse software). This connection works as follows:

On the main page of the repository, the user will find a link to the integration dashboard. The user has to be logged in with an institutional account of the KU Leuven. You need to select your data source and authorize the connection (single sign-on is used for most cases). The second step is to select the destination dataset, this could also be a new draft dataset. Then, the dashboard will take you to a comparison page, where you can see the files that are in your source and the files in the destination dataset. New files, unchanged files, and changed files are indicated. Files can be copied, deleted, or mirrored, also in bulk. After submitting the changes, the dataset is processed and the user will receive an email if the workflow is completed. A link to the dataset will be displayed.

The depositor will need to add metadata, check the license, and file restrictions, and submit for review within the Dataverse interface.

2b. Motivations for developing deposit workflow

The long list of already existing deposit workflows shows that there are multiple use cases and reasons for developing a deposit workflow. We have distinguished five main reasons:

1. Lower the threshold for publishing and sharing data
Most of the workflows with a push mechanism start at the platform which the depositor is already familiar with, such as Github, OSF or Yoda. This is of course convenient for the user, and it might lower the threshold to deposit data at all. Users who would otherwise not even think about sharing data, are now confronted with a simple way to deposit data into a repository.
2. Eliminate the extra step of downloading files before uploading
A deposit workflow enables the depositor to upload directly to the repository without having to download the data to their local file system first. Depending on the settings, synchronization of the source data with the dataset can even be automated. This can be an important feature for larger datasets.
3. Retaining folder structure
If a user would like to upload files with a folder structure, the user has to upload the files in one zip-file. A deposit workflow can offer a better user experience when uploading a folder structure, by automatically creating the file paths associated with a file.
4. Support for publishing datasets with large files/ many files
The DVUploader was developed to overcome the difficulties that can be experienced when uploading large files, many files, or files with multiple subdirectories through the user interface. They also mention that the tool can be helpful when new files are being generated/added to a directory and Dataverse needs to be updated with just the new files, and when uploading of files needs to be automated, e.g., added to an instrument or analysis script or program.

2c. Considerations

Which workflow is most suitable for a depositor depends on several different aspects. The number of datasets to deposit over time, the technical savviness of the user, and the platform where the research data has been stored during the research phase all play a role. But also the characteristics of the dataset are important, e.g., the number of files, file size, and directory structure.

If a researcher does a one-time-only deposit, filling in the metadata form directly in the repository and selecting files from local storage is probably sufficient. For depositors that have multiple datasets to archive, or need to do bulk actions, a workflow that involves SWORD or the DVUploader in combination with a self-produced automation makes more sense.

In developing a deposit workflow, the user friendliness must also be taken into account. The large number of push workflows indicate that 'being where the user is' is an important aspect. A growing number of institutes seem to make use of Yoda (iRODS), so a connection with this platform becomes of more importance. The same can be said of the SURF Research Drive, almost all universities (WO) and universities of applied sciences (HBO) offer this platform to their researchers. This is corroborated by our interactions during the input sessions, where iRODS-based data management systems or SURF Research Drive have also been mentioned as important environments where researchers have their data during the research phase of the data life cycle. We also see an increase in the universities with a DataverseNL repository system for publishing and sharing their data. This stresses the need to build connections between the systems where data is stored during research (i.e. Yoda, Research Drive) and the repository where data is published and shared (i.e. DataverseNL, Data Stations).

Lastly, another point to consider is the file size. Most repositories have set limits to the file size that can be uploaded, because of technical or cost limitations. For Dataverse repositories, it is known that uploading large files (>9.5GB), or a lot of files (>1000) at the same time, is problematic via the user interface. Uploading via the API can sometimes keep these problems at bay. If a Dataverse repository makes use of Object Storage, an external storage service provided by SURF, there is a useful configuration setting available that defines that uploads via the API are 'direct uploads' to the Object Storage, whereas normal uploads through the UI are first processed by local storage.

Push vs. Pull workflows

While the push integrations are located conveniently for the depositors, this type of workflow also has its disadvantages.

Setting up a push deposit workflow requires cooperation and investment from external parties. If connections with multiple data sources are desired, the same steps have to be repeated to develop each workflow. Furthermore, the push deposit workflows will be more difficult to maintain in the future. If the repository changes its technical requirements, the external party will need to cooperate to adjust the connection. This does not only apply to technical changes. A change in the required metadata fields in the target repository might cause the connection to fail. Furthermore, if the starting point of the deposit workflow offers additional and/or other metadata fields that the repository does not support, it will be impossible to save them appropriately.

In addition, minor variations between the behavior of each workflow may occur. This is already apparent if you look at the difference in versioning methods for a dataset that is deposited through GitHub and a direct deposit. When synchronizing data from GitHub with Dataverse, every existing data file is deleted, and subsequently all the files are added again - new files and files that were in the previous version. The 'chain of evidence' over the different versions will be lost and this is bad practice. Worse still, many of the push workflows listed in the table above do not account for versioning at all. For example, the OH-Smart deposit form doesn't allow a user to edit an already existing dataset, such as alterations to terms/file restrictions and metadata. A better method would be to add only

new files, and update the existing ones, as is currently the case if you would use the web interface of the Dataverse repository.

The main drawback of a pull workflow is that the starting point is different from the place where they manage their data. The many efforts made to create push mechanisms from research platforms show that there is a substantial need for this. A researcher that hosts all his data in SURF Research Drive would find the SRDC very convenient.

Within a pull deposit workflow, depositors have to select the files they want to upload, and in many cases there is no real integration to upload the data directly from another platform, rather files need to be downloaded to local storage first. This can often result in losing the hierarchical structure of data when uploading it to Dataverse.

Datasets with files larger than 9.5 GB, or with a large amount of files (more than 1000) are problematic to upload through the pull mechanism of Dataverse deposit form.

Lastly, if the host of the data doesn't offer an API to connect to, there will be no option to pull the files.

2d. Recommendations

Taking all of this into account, the following recommendations can be made.

The deposit workflows that are based on a push mechanism have as a weakness that the transfer of metadata and dataset versioning are difficult to maintain. The available metadata fields at the data storage place can be incompatible with the selected repository. It is technically difficult to create a complete set of metadata, license, and terms of use information without visiting the webpage of the repository of choice and adding it there. So, if a new workflow has to be developed, it should either solve the incompatibility issues, or the workflow should be focussed on the transfer of files alone to avoid these issues.

As most workflows are developed with user convenience in mind, it would be worthwhile to investigate if the push workflows from iRods/Yoda and SURF Research Drive can be made more sustainable by mutual agreements on functionality specifications and maintenance.

Tools that are made to circumvent upload problems such as the DVUploader lack an intuitive user interface. Maybe some effort can be made to see if this tool can be better integrated in the Dataverse User Interface.

When creating another deposit workflow, or extending the already existing ones, added value can be found in functionality on file level. If files are the focus, why not offer the user tools to make the files as suitable as possible for publication and reuse? Some ideas may include automatic conversion into preferred file formats, adding subtitles to audio files, named entity recognition, and automated checks on privacy sensitive content.

The Dataverse Integration dashboard developed by the KU Leuven seems to be a very well executed pull deposit workflow. It connects to the platforms used by their researchers, and

solves common problems with file upload and versioning. However, it is specifically aimed at researchers at the KU Leuven. If such an integration dashboard would be used as an example for the SSHOC-NL deposit workflow, the dashboard should be easily accessible and findable for the Dutch SSH researchers. As it is a pull mechanism, the tool won't be accessible from the data storage point, so users will have to be in the know about the dashboard. Furthermore, it might be useful to investigate if such a dashboard could connect to multiple repositories, as Dutch SSH researchers might want to deposit somewhere else.

Conclusions and next steps

In light of the requirements emerging from the input sessions and the analysis of advantages and disadvantages of various deposit workflows already available, we start with the following features:

Licences

- The most basic adjustment in the way Dataverse supports licences: add distinct licences for restricted and open files in a dataset.
- Analyse existing licences, define elements from which licences should be 'assembled', find out most important variants of each element, design a modular set of building blocks which accommodate the 80% most frequently occurring use cases.
- Find the most suitable structured language (e.g. ODRL) for expressing these building blocks in machine readable language.

Direct deposit

- Work together with SURF, who have the capacity to realize some push-mechanisms from their data services, by way of quick wins.
 - SURF Research Drive > Dataverse / OH-SMART-like deposit interface
SURF is already developing a push-based deposit mechanism (SRDC, see chapter 2 above). They are willing to collaborate with DANS to make this available, both to the Data Station SSH and to an OH-SMART-like deposit interface.
 - Yoda (iRODS based) > Dataverse / OH-SMART-like deposit interface.
Talks are underway to find out how SURF and DANS can collaborate in making a direct connection possible.
 - RUG RDMS (iRODS based) > Dataverse / OH-SMART-like deposit interface
- Test these push mechanisms
- Make sure that the push mechanisms focus on transfer of *data files* alone to avoid incompatibility issues of software and metadata schemes.
- Design a flexible architecture to add functionality to make the files as suitable as possible for publication and reuse, by way of satellite microservices.
 - automatic conversion into preferred file formats
 - adding subtitles to audio files
 - named entity recognition
 - automated checks on privacy sensitive content.

Subsequent steps:

- Create more documentation, also promoting the adoption of Data Access Protocols and Data Availability Statements in research data management processes (see 1.e).
- Retrieve metadata from source systems (CRIS, VRE, Preregistration) for new data deposits.
- Link research data and research software through PIDs, for instance in the knowledge graph developed in SSHOC-NL.

- Deposit code and data, each in their own proper repository, in one go.
- Explore ways to set up a risk classification system for research data.
- Explore language agnostic description of data, e.g. through the approach proposed by LinkML.

Appendix A. Questionnaire

- For what reason do your researchers *archive* their research data?
- For what reason do your researchers *publish* their research data?
- What aspect is more important for your researchers: archiving their research data for the long term, or publishing their research data?
- On what platform(s) do your researchers manage their research data *during the research phase*? And why do they use that platform (or those platforms)?
- On what platform(s) do your researchers currently archive and/or publish their research data for reuse *after the project phase ends*? And why do they use that/those platform(s)?
- Would it be of interest to integrate or link the platforms that are used during the research phase and the platforms used after the project phase ends to facilitate the easy transfer of (meta)data from one platform to the other?
- Which functionalities are missing from current archiving/publishing platforms?
- Do the functionalities of the archiving/publishing platform align with your institute's policy with regard to data management and the rightsholdership and responsibilities of the research data?
- Are there any particular metadata schemes which should be available for the research data generated and/or used by your researchers (please specify)?
- Which controlled vocabularies do your researchers use (if at all)?
- What access conditions (open, restricted, closed, embargo, retention period) do your researchers need for their research data? Are these available in the archiving/publishing platform?
- What kinds of data / data formats are mainly deposited by your researchers, and what are file sizes of data files?
- How can the user-friendliness (either in a technical sense or in terms of training, guidance, or support) of the archiving/publishing platform be improved?
- If the archiving/publishing platform your researchers use would be improved (with respect to functionalities, user-friendliness, training/guidance/support, availability of metadata schemes, controlled vocabularies, access conditions, and licences), would you expect an increase in data deposits from your institution? If so, what volume would this increase amount to on an annual basis?
- Are there any other issues, topics, questions, concerns, etc. that you run into during your daily work with archiving/publishing research data that you would like to discuss with us and your peers?

Appendix B. User stories

Improving functionalities

The user stories we formulated with regard to working with restricted data are as follows (see the Glossary of Terms at the end of this appendix for the definition of terms identifying roles within the research data management process):

As a **researcher who has data and metadata which is a result of their research (data creator)**

I want **an option to upload existing metadata (to Dataverse)**
so that **I can reuse information that is already available somewhere else**

As a **principal investigator who uses Dataverse**

I want **to be able to change the folder structure**
so that **I can change the folders after uploading if necessary**

As a **researcher who uses Dataverse**

I want **to be able to pin files to the top**
so that **a README file is always on top**

Remarks:

Already possible in Dataverse, but requires a specific configuration and some instructions for the use

As a **data (re)user (data consumer) who accesses a repository**

I want **to be able to download individual folders and/or individual files**
so that **I can download only what I need**

Remarks:

Already possible in Dataverse

As a **data collector who uses a data administration system, such as Dataverse**

I want **to be able to create / upload folders**
so that **I can organise the data in a logical way**

Remarks:

Already possible in Dataverse

Working with restricted data

The user stories we formulated with regard to working with restricted data are:

As a **data steward**
I want **better licences**
so that **the conditions of reuse are more clearly formulated**

As a **data steward**
I want **to have the tools to do a proper data classification**
so that **I know the level of sensitivity and associated security measures**

As a **data re(user) of restricted access datasets**
I want **to have better instructions about the access procedure**
so that **I know what to expect**

As a **data steward**
I want **to have a clear procedure for (all the stages of) data access**
so that **I know how the procedure is organised and what stages I have to follow**

As a **principal investigator responsible for access to data created in our research**
I want **multiple tiers of restricted data**
so that **I can be more flexible in choosing access conditions and licences**

Remarks:
already possible in Dataverse, up to a point: either closed, restricted or open access, on file level

As a **principal investigator responsible for access to data created in our research**
I want **to be able to restrict individual files in a dataset**
so that **I can make parts of my data open and restrict the ones I need**

Remarks:
already possible in Dataverse

Getting support

The user stories we formulated with regard to getting support are:

As a **data steward**
I want **a clear overview of available services and their pros and cons**
so that **I can advise researchers what platform to use in their project**

As a **DataverseNL administrator managing their organisation's instance of Dataverse**
I want **peer-support**
so that **I do not only have to rely on DANS**

Follow-up session

In the following set of user stories, some are actually combinations of the user stories as they were submitted during the workshop. Some of the user stories lacked the third part, the goal of the improvement (“so that”), in which cases we have inferred this goal ourselves, putting it between [square brackets].

As a **researcher**
I want **to have advice on formatting code and data**
so that **I know how to share code and data in an easily accessible and understandable way**

As a **researcher**
I want **to have access to an open interface connecting my research environment and storage to a repository**
so that **I can easily transfer data and metadata**

As a **principal investigator and data steward**
I want **an easy tool helping me to choose a repository**
so that **I can find the relevant repository for my data**

As a **researcher or principal investigator and data steward**
I want **to provide my metadata only once, then have them harvested, from source systems such as preregistration, DMP, SMP, CRIS, lab journals, scripts, privacy assessments and publications, including all the PIDs**
so that **the metadata descriptions are standardized and no time is lost doing double work**

As a **researcher and data steward**
I want **to have clear instructions for researchers**
so that **they know how to upload data and metadata and understand the added value of services**

As a **data steward or data manager**
I want **to have an overview of all deposited data**
so that **I can monitor and report on FAIR data management within my institution**

As a **data steward or data manager**
I want **to automate identification of personal or otherwise sensitive data**
so that **I can assess the appropriate access conditions and licence of a data deposit in less time and with more certainty**

As a **software steward (preservation manager / data manager)**
I want **to incorporate code in our data management system (iRODS, YoDa)**
so that **I can feed them into a deposit pipeline which leads to a repository**

As a **research infrastructure architect**
I want **a modular software stack**
so that **interoperability is increased**

As a **service provider (infrastructure provider)**
I want **APIs**
so that **connections with my infrastructure can be made**

Remarks:
Already available for Dataverse.

As a **data manager**
I want **to maintain my folder structure intact during deposit**
so that **errors in access restrictions are reduced and reuse is facilitated**

Remarks:
Already possible in Dataverse but requires a specific configuration and some instructions for the use.

As a **researcher (data collector or data creator)**
I want **to have audio tools**
so that **I can improve the quality of samples**

Remarks:
Request relevant to a specific user group.

As a **researcher**
I want **to extract variables and value ranges**
so that **[the relevance of my dataset can be evaluated more easily by potential reusers]**

Remarks:
Request relevant to a specific user group; already possible in the ODISSEI portal, up to a point, and also facilitated by the adoption of the Croissant format of metadata export.

Glossary of Terms

This glossary of terms is based on The Reference Model for Social Sciences and Humanities Data Infrastructures (RM-SSH)²², developed in the precursor project to SSHOC (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud) called DASISH (Digital Services Infrastructure for Social Sciences and Humanities)²³. As a reference model RM-SSH defines the concepts and relationships of research and data infrastructures in the social sciences and/or humanities.

In the following glossary we attempt to contextualise the actors described in the user stories with respect to definitions pertinent to data deposit, management, provision and (re-)use in the humanities and social sciences as defined in the RM-SSH. It should be noted that only selected non-system and system roles have been initially selected from the RM-SSH which are pertinent to this report. However, in further defining processes, such as data ingest, further system and non-system roles and behaviour need to be defined as well. It should be noted that a system may include human-mediated roles but generally refers to digital systems.

Data Collector: a person who records observations and registers these into a dataset.

Data Manager: a person or organization that is responsible for ensuring the quality of the research data during its ingest and management.

Data (Re)User: an agent that requests and receives the research data (for further use as a **Data Consumer**). Access to the data may be direct or mediated via a third-party.

Data Steward: a person (or organization) that performs the role of a **Data Provider**, responsible for making the research data from the **PI (Data Owner)** available for the data (re)user (**Data Consumer**).

Dataverse: performs the role of a **Data Administration System** which is responsible for registering the data products for management purposes.

DataverseNL administrator: a person who manages a **Data Administration System** for the registration of data products for management purposes. In this case an installation of Dataverse performs the functions required of the system.

Preservation Manager: a person that is responsible for generating data products and entering/registering them in the data administration service.

Principal Investigator (PI): a person or organisation that owns (**Data Owner**) the data and determines the conditions for deposit/access with the **Data Manager**.

Repository: can perform several tasks including that of a **Data Retrieval System** which is a system that enables retrieval of research data. Data retrieval includes access control (and thus, authorization). Examples that perform this role include Dataverse.

Researcher: is a person, group, or organisation that is responsible for the data creation and therefore performs the role of a **Data Creator**.

Service Provider (infrastructure provider): an organization which utilises a **Data Discovery System**, a system facilitating discovery of research data and its context, and a **Data Retrieval System**, to provide a service to the Service Provider's designated community.

²² <https://sites.google.com/a/dans.knaw.nl/reference-model-for-ssh-data-infrastructure/home?authuser=0>

²³ <https://www.cessda.eu/Development-Impact/Past-Activities/DASISH>